

EVALUATION OF INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS PRIORITISED SOLUTIONS

DELIVERABLE 3.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the evaluation and prioritisation of Industrial Symbiosis (IS) solutions within the context of the SYMBA project, which aims to advance the circular economy and bio-based industrial ecosystems across the European Union. The project applies the Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methodology to assess the maturity of various IS solutions, using five readiness levels: Symbiosis Readiness Level (SymRL), Organisational Readiness Level (ORL), Legal and Ethical Readiness Level (LRL), Societal Readiness Level (SRL), and Environmental Readiness Level (ERL).

This deliverable (D3.3) describes the results of applying MCDA to prioritise IS solutions, drawing on a collaborative process involving both internal and external stakeholders. The report outlines the methodology, including the application of the evaluation criteria, the assignment of weighting factors, and the categorisation of solutions by their maturity levels: Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced. Based on these evaluations, the report also provides practical guidelines for stakeholders to implement and improve IS solutions, including recommendations tailored to the maturity level of each solution. The final outcomes of this process are intended to support the effective adoption and scaling of IS solutions, contributing to the EU's broader sustainability and resource efficiency goals.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ERL - Environmental Readiness Levels

GHG - Greenhouse Gas

IS - Industrial Symbiosis

LRL - Legal & ethical Readiness Level

MCDCA - Multicriteria Decision Analysis

ORL - Organisational Readiness Level

SRL - Societal Readiness Level

SymRL - Symbiosis Readiness Levels

RL – Readiness level

WP – Work package

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Industrial Symbiosis (IS) solutions are essential to advancing the circular economy, turning waste into valuable resources, reducing environmental pollution, and optimising resource efficiency across entire value chains. These solutions foster a more sustainable and interconnected industrial landscape by unlocking business opportunities through the reuse of undervalued resources such as energy, materials, water, infrastructure, and expertise. Grounded in the 4R hierarchy —Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Recover— IS goes beyond conventional waste management by promoting closed-loop systems that increase efficiency, reduce waste, and harmonise environmental and economic objectives.

The SYMBA project aims to transform Industrial Symbiosis practices across the European Union by developing innovative, region-specific approaches tailored to local bio-based ecosystems. SYMBA aligns with the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and draws on the collective expertise of its consortium to design and validate a new IS methodology for the bio-based sector.

Key goals of the SYMBA project include:

- Establish criteria for selecting regional hubs and develop a robust AI-driven database.
- Integrate tools such as a waste relationship matrix, monitoring systems, and frameworks for enhancing collaboration and networking across EU regions.
- Strengthen cooperation within bio-based sectors, including packaging, agri-food, textiles, wastewater management, and waste valorisation.

SYMBA will enable the creation of sustainable industrial networks for long-term partnerships. The outcomes of the project will empower local stakeholders to implement innovative IS solutions, accelerating the shift toward a circular, resource-efficient economy. This initiative will help preserve natural resources like water and soil, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and drive the transformation of bio-based industries, contributing to a more resilient and sustainable future.

1.2. Scope and objectives of the deliverable

To achieve the overarching objectives of the SYMBA project —namely, fostering the replication of innovative IS solutions tailored to regional bio-based ecosystems— Work Package 3 (WP3) plays a central role in consolidating and evaluating existing knowledge. WP3 is structured around two interrelated phases: i) the systematic collection and mapping of IS solutions (Task 3.1), and ii) the classification and prioritisation of the mapped solutions based on multidimensional readiness criteria (Tasks 3.2 and 3.3).

This deliverable (D3.3) presents the outcomes of Task 3.3, which focuses on the final evaluation and prioritisation of IS solutions using a structured methodology rooted in the SYMBA framework. The deliverable also provides practical guidelines for applying the evaluation framework. These guidelines are intended to support stakeholders and regional actors in selecting and implementing IS solutions that are contextually appropriate and aligned with the broader EU Bioeconomy Strategy.

This deliverable is structured into three main sections, in addition to the present introductory part. Section 2 details the methodological approach adopted to derive the final weighting factors for the evaluation criteria. Section 3 presents the results obtained by applying these weighting factors to the mapped industrial symbiosis solutions. Finally, Section 4 offers practical guidelines for applying the developed methodology to other IS contexts, along with a set of recommendations aimed at enhancing the implementation of industrial symbiosis solutions.

2. METHODOLOGY: MULTICRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS

Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is a structured methodology designed to support decision-making in situations involving multiple, often conflicting, criteria. Unlike traditional single-objective approaches, MCDA enables decision-makers to consider a diverse set of quantitative and qualitative factors —such as cost, environmental impact, social acceptability, and technical feasibility— and to assess how these interact in complex decision contexts. The process typically involves four key steps: i) identifying the relevant decision criteria; ii) assigning weights that represent the relative importance of each criterion; iii) evaluating and scoring the available alternatives based on these criteria; and iv) aggregating the results using formal decision rules to rank or prioritise the alternatives (Bystrzanowska & Tobiszewski, 2018).

MCDA is especially valuable in domains like sustainability assessment, environmental policy, industrial planning, and technology selection, where trade-offs between economic, social, and ecological goals must be carefully balanced (Cinelli et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2011). The method offers flexibility in accommodating stakeholder preferences, integrating expert judgment, and enabling participatory decision-making processes. In the context of the SYMBA project, MCDA is applied to evaluate and prioritise IS solutions by incorporating weighted readiness criteria —such as Symbiosis, Environmental, Societal, Organisational, and Legal/Ethical Readiness Levels—derived from stakeholder input. This helps guide the selection of IS solutions that are not only technically viable but also contextually relevant and sustainable.

2.1. Implementation approach

In the framework of the project, MCDA was implemented in two different rounds as part of an iterative and collaborative process to evaluate and rank IS solutions (Figure 1).

1. The list of IS solutions, classified as approaches, methodologies and platforms (outcome from *T3.1-Data collection on Industrial Symbiosis solutions*), was evaluated and ranked according to the depicted criteria (Symbiosis, Environmental, Societal, Organisational, and Legal/Ethical Readiness Levels) and prioritised based on internally co-created weighting factors, generating an initial list of prioritised IS solutions (*T3.2 Internal co-creation and weighting*).
2. An iterative validation process was then conducted, involving external stakeholders who participated through an online questionnaire and a collaborative session to define external weighting factors for the same set of criteria. These new insights were used to re-evaluate the previously prioritised solutions, leading to the production of a final, refined list of prioritised IS solutions that reflects both internal and external stakeholder perspectives.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the approach followed in the MCDA to evaluate and prioritise IS solutions.

2.1.1. Internal co-creation and weighting

In T3.2, specifically in D3.2, over 150 IS solutions — i.e., those derived from T3.1 and D3.1 — were evaluated and prioritised by systematically applying the MCDA framework. The IS solutions were: i) evaluated against each readiness level criterion (Symbiosis, Environmental, Societal, Organisational, and Legal/Ethical), yielding individual score values for each criterion; ii) weighted using internally co-created weighting factors, resulting in a single aggregated score for each IS solution; and iii) prioritised and listed according to their classification as approaches, methodologies, or platforms.

It should be noted that careful weighting of criteria is crucial for effective decision-making. Hence, accurately representing the relative importance of various factors is ensured, which facilitates a balanced consideration of trade-offs. Therefore, assigning appropriate weights enhances the robustness, credibility, and relevance of the decision-making process, ultimately leading to well-informed and actionable solutions. Thus, a set of initial weighting factors was collaboratively developed by the project's industrial partners during an internal co-creation process (series of online workshop sessions). These interactive sessions facilitated joint reflection on the relative importance of various evaluation criteria, ensuring that the weights reflected the industrial priorities and practical insights of the stakeholders involved. Table 1 shows the weighting factors obtained during the internal co-creation process. Likewise, Table 2 depicts the industrial stakeholders involved in the internal co-creation process.

Table 1. Weighting factors derived from the internal co-creation process.

READINESS LEVEL	WEIGHTING FACTOR (%)
Organisational Readiness Level (ORL)	15
Legal & ethical Readiness Level (LRL)	15
Societal Readiness Level (SRL)	15
Environmental Readiness Levels (ERL)	25
Symbiosis Readiness Levels (SymRL)	30

Table 2. List of industrial partners stakeholders involved in the internal co-creation process.

ACRONYM	LEGAL NAME	COUNTRY
CIRCE	Fundación Circe Centro De Investigación De Recursos Y Consumos Energéticos	Spain
CET	Fundación Centro Gallego De Investigaciones Del Agua	Spain
AIMPLAS	Asociación De investigación De Materiales Plásticos Y Conexas	Spain
BBEPP	Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant	Belgium
CTB	Centre Scientifique & Technique Del'industrie Textile Belge ASBL	Belgium
NVMNT	Novamont SPA	Italy
ENCO	ENCO SRL	Italy

The resulting co-created weighting factors were subsequently applied within the MCDA framework to rank the proposed IS solutions. Based on the final aggregated scores, the solutions were prioritised to support informed and consensus-driven decision-making. The evaluation results and final scores, detailing the prioritised IS solutions, are available in the deliverable **D3.2- List and analysis of prioritised Industrial Symbiosis solutions**.

2.1.2. External co-creation and weighting

External stakeholder experts were convened following the quadruple helix of social innovation, which integrates representatives from academia, industry, government, and community (in this case, specialised in the subject matter) (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009). This structured approach ensures the integration of scientific knowledge, market-driven priorities, regulatory insights, and specialised community perspectives in both the questionnaire-based evaluation exercise and co-creation activities. The methodology specifically targeted expert input rather than general public opinion, as the technical nature of the assessment required specialised knowledge. Additionally, participants' profiles and their respective helix affiliations were carefully considered when evaluating score changes in both the questionnaire and co-creation sessions, ensuring balanced representation within this collaborative innovation ecosystem.

To both enhance the evaluation framework's robustness through complementary expertise and address potential biases from internal prioritisation, a second round of co-creation was conducted with external expert stakeholders through two steps. First, a questionnaire to determine how different readiness levels should be weighted when assessing IS based on stakeholders' expertise and their prioritisation of each readiness level. Second, an online co-creation session to evaluate prioritised solutions and their readiness levels, while reviewing, validating, and refining the MCDA approach, enriching it with quantitative and qualitative insights and expert feedback.

The first step in this external co-creation process was the design and distribution of a targeted questionnaire, aimed at both validating the relevance of the readiness levels and exploring how experts prioritise them. This questionnaire served to quantify expert judgments, capture complementary perspectives across different professional backgrounds, and lay the foundations for the subsequent step two, the collaborative discussions.

As part of the questionnaire design, two complementary exercises were included to explore how participants assessed the importance of each readiness level. On the one hand, respondents were asked to rank the five readiness levels from most to least important. On the other hand, they were asked to distribute 100 points among those same levels based on their perceived relative significance. These two different questions served distinct yet interrelated methodological purposes:

- The **ranking task**, reflected in the first Question of the questionnaire (Table 3), functioned as a mechanism for quick prioritisation. It revealed which dimensions were perceived as most and least critical, making it especially effective for highlighting polarities– what matters most and least.
- The **weighting task**, in the second question, introduced quantitative nuance by allowing participants to express the relative importance of all five criteria. This added granularity and helped quantify perceived trade-offs between dimensions that may be close in priority.

The questionnaire included six questions (Table 3), two of which focused on understanding the background of the respondents (questions 5 and 6), while the remaining four targeted the readiness level evaluation (questions 1 to 4).

Table 3. Questions presented to the external stakeholders on online questionnaire.

<p>1. Rank the following readiness levels from 1 (least important) to 5 (most important) in terms of their significance for successful Industrial Symbiosis implementation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • __ Symbiosis Readiness Level (SymRL) – Technology, Business, Ecology, Management • __ Organisational Readiness Level (ORL) – Capacity & Commitment of organisations • __ Legal & Ethical Readiness Level (LRL) – Compliance with regulations & ethics • __ Societal Readiness Level (SRL) – Public acceptance, partnerships, and education • __ Environmental Readiness Level (ERL) – Sustainability and circular economy impact.
<p>2. Distribute 100 points among the five readiness levels based on their relative importance (Total must add up to 100 points).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Symbiosis Readiness Level (SymRL): __ points • Organisational Readiness Level (ORL): __ points • Legal & Ethical Readiness Level (LRL): __ points • Societal Readiness Level (SRL): __ points • Environmental Readiness Level (ERL): __ points
<p>3. If you believe a particular readiness level is critical, briefly explain why it should receive more weight in the evaluation process. (Open-ended response)</p>

4. Would you like to suggest any additional criteria that should be considered when evaluating IS solutions?
(Open-ended response)

5. Have you participated in any industrial symbiosis projects? If so, please specify.

Yes (please specify) _____

No

6. What is your role in the Industrial Symbiosis ecosystem? (Select one or more)

Academia

Industry

Government

Community

Other (please specify): _____

Twenty IS experts answered the questionnaire across five profiles: government, academia, industry, community and other. Table 4 shows the number of responses for each profile.

Table 4. Number of responses for IS expert profile.

Profiles	Number of responses
Industry	7
Scientific community	7
Other	3
Government	2
Community	1

Delving into the results of Question 1, on average, the Symbiosis Readiness Level (SymRL) was ranked as the most important criteria whilst the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) as the least important criteria (Figure 2). The Organisational Readiness Level (ORL), the Environmental Readiness Level (ERL), and the Legal & Ethical Readiness Level (LRL) criterion were ranked second, third and fourth, respectively, in terms of importance.

Figure 2. Average ranking of readiness levels (Question 1).

Focusing on the individual responses, almost 50% of the respondents (9 out of 20) ranked SymRL as the most important criterion (ranking of 1), coinciding with the average ranking. This was not the case for the remaining readiness levels, where most individual answers did not match the average ranking.

As shown in Table 4, the majority of the consulted IS experts came from the scientific community (7 out of 20) and the industry (7 out of 20). Figure 3 shows the average rankings for these two expert profiles. In this sense, some differences were evident. For example, there was a significant disparity in the ranking of the ERL criterion, which was ranked first in importance by industry representatives and fourth by those from the scientific community. At first glance, the inverse conclusion will be expected, showcasing how much environmental aspects and performance have become a focus of industrial enterprises. As expected from the results shown in Figure 2, for both the industry (4.2) and the scientific community (3.9) the SRL is the least significant.

Figure 3. Average ranking of readiness levels for industry and scientific community respondents (Question 1).

Furthermore, in Question 2, respondents were asked to distribute 100 points among the readiness levels. The average results showed that –again– SymRL was considered the most important criterion, receiving 26.6 points out of 100 available, followed by ORL, LRL and ERL with 21.4, 21.1, and 18.4 points, respectively. Finally, SRL was the least important criterion with 11.6 points (Figure 4). This lower prioritisation of SRL can be attributed to the highly technical nature of industrial symbiosis assessment. In this context, expert stakeholders tend to focus on immediate operational and technical feasibility rather than broader social implications (Vahidzadeh et al., 2021; Terrapon-Pfaff et al., 2017).

Figure 4. Average points assigned to the readiness levels -out of 100 (Question 2).

In the same manner as in the ranking (Question 1), when differentiating by type of expert profile, a similar pattern was obtained for ERL, which showed the largest difference between industrial and scientific community respondents, with 15.3 and 25.7 points distributed, respectively (Figure 5). Conversely, both the industrial and scientific community gave more than 20 points to SymRL and LRL.

Figure 5. Average points assigned by the industry and scientific respondents to the readiness levels -out of 100 (Question 2).

Interestingly, when comparing the rankings of the readiness levels based on perceived importance (Question 1) and point distribution (Question 2), there is a high degree of consistency for some criteria. SymRL ranked first, ORL ranked second, and SRL ranked fifth in both questions. However, ERL and LRL swapped positions between third and fourth place across the two questions.

A higher degree of variation appears when these results are broken down by expert profile (Figure 6). Among industry respondents, only two criteria maintained the same position across both questions: ERL was ranked first, and SymRL was ranked third. In contrast, respondents from the scientific community showed alignment on three criteria: SymRL in first place, ERL in fourth place, and SRL in fifth place, indicating a more stable perception of the extremes, but some variation in the mid-tier rankings.

Figure 6. Average ranking and points given by experts according to their profile.

Questions 3 and 4 were open-ended, allowing participants to provide feedback and yielding valuable responses. Regarding Question 3 “*If you believe a particular readiness level is critical, briefly explain why it should receive more weight in the evaluation process*”, most respondents mentioned that all criteria were important, but highlighted that SymRL and ORL could be considered more critical, as both encompass aspects already included in the other readiness levels. As for questions 4 “*Would you like to suggest any additional criteria that should be considered when evaluating IS solutions?*”, some respondents mentioned possible additional criteria. However, after further examinations of the readiness definitions (as presented in **D3.2 - List and analysis of prioritised industrial symbiosis solutions**), it was determined that the suggested additional criteria were already considered (Table 5).

Table 5. IS experts suggested additional criteria.

IS experts suggested criteria	Related readiness level
Scalability potential	SymRL
Data accessibility and transparency	SymRL and ORL
Cultural aspects	SRL

Taken together, the results showed a broad consensus around the central role of SymRL and the lower priority of SRL. The variations between ERL and LRL, suggest deeper differences in how certain readiness dimensions are interpreted. These differences should not be seen as contradictions but rather as evidence of the layered and context-sensitive nature of IS evaluation.

Essentially, these findings must be understood within the methodological context: participants responded individually, without deliberation, and based on their professional experience. As such, differences in ranking versus weighting, and variations between profiles, reflect the richness of the data rather than its inconsistency. They highlight the importance of combining both methods to identify points of alignment and divergence.

In sum, the questionnaire results offered a valuable baseline for building a robust and inclusive evaluation framework. Thus, the observed patterns are revisited and contextualised in the next steps of the process- the co-creation workshop- which introduced a collective sense-making dynamic to confirm, challenge, or modify individual insights.

Building on the results of the previously discussed online questionnaire, an **online co-creation session** with external stakeholders was held on March 18, 2025, as part of the second phase of the MCDA framework evaluation process. A total of 11 participants actively contributed to the session. Although the number of attendees was limited, the session aimed to ensure diversity and complementarity by inviting a targeted selection of experts with varied profiles across the IS ecosystem. The selection followed a purposive sampling logic, seeking to balance academic, industrial, public sector, and civil society perspectives.

The objective of the session was not to replicate the questionnaire, but to validate and interpret its results through collective reflection, capture qualitative insights, and identify potential refinements in the readiness levels definitions and evaluation logic. The session was structured into six thematic blocks as depicted in Table 6.

Table 6. Detail of the 6 thematic blocks conducted in the online co-creation session.

<p><u>1. Warm-Up & Icebreaker (5-10 min)</u> Goal: Get participants comfortable and engaged. Miro Question: "What comes to your mind when you hear 'Industrial Symbiosis'?" (Word Cloud)</p> <p>◆ Activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Show responses live on the screen. <p>Pick a few interesting words and ask participants to elaborate.</p>
<p><u>2. Understanding Priorities (15 min)</u> Goal: Identify what matters most for IS evaluation. Miro Question: "Share and discuss the result of the ranking IS solutions questionnaire.</p> <p>◆ Activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Show real-time ranking results. ● Facilitate discussion: "Why do you think [Top-Ranked Criterion] is most important?" <p>Encourage debate between different viewpoints.</p>
<p><u>3. Co-Creation Brainstorming (20 min)</u> Goal: Gather fresh ideas for IS evaluation. Miro Question: "What other aspects should be included in the evaluation of IS solutions?" (Open-ended response)</p> <p>◆ Activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Let participants enter ideas. ● Group similar responses live. <p>Discuss key themes: "What surprises you about these suggestions?"</p>
<p><u>4. Testing Evaluation Methods (15 min)</u> Goal: Validate and refine IS evaluation approaches. Miro Question: "How effective do you think Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is for evaluating IS solutions?" (Likert Scale: 1-5)</p> <p>◆ Activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discuss results: "For those who rated it high, why? For those who rated it low, what's missing?" ● Invite participants to suggest alternative evaluation approaches. <p>Collect real-world examples from their experience.</p>

5. Defining Future Priorities (15 min)

Goal: Identify where IS solutions should focus next.

Miro Question: "**Which area should IS solutions focus on for future sustainability?**" (Multiple Choice: Waste Valorisation, Energy Recovery, Digitalization, Regional Collaboration, etc.)

◆ **Activity:**

- Analyse trends in responses.

Ask: "What actions can we take to support these priorities?"

6. Closing (10 min)

Goal: Ensure takeaways and action points.

Miro Question: "**What's one key takeaway from today's session?**" (Open-ended response)

◆ **Activity:**

- Show responses live.

Summarise

The prioritisation of readiness levels, explored in Question 2 of the co-creation workshop, prompted general agreement with the order established in the questionnaire. Participants rated their level of agreement with the weighting distribution at 3.9 out of 5, confirming that the SymRL was correctly prioritised, while SRL was perceived as less critical. The same score (3.9) was registered regarding the clarity and completeness of the readiness levels definitions. Some participants suggested refining the societal dimension to include public participation, local governance structures, and cultural acceptance, while others emphasised the legal and ethical dimension as a decisive factor in regional implementation.

Regarding potential improvements to the evaluation framework, as addressed in Question 3, participants identified complementary aspects to consider. These included:

- The scalability of IS solutions and their potential for replication.
- Data transparency to support trust and comparability.
- The role of infrastructure availability as an enabling condition.
- The importance of behavioural and cultural factors under societal readiness.

Most of these suggestions aligned with elements already covered in the framework, but the discussion added nuance and helped clarify where overlaps should be disentangled, or definitions sharpened.

On the suitability of MCDA as an evaluation method, discussed in Question 4, participants expressed moderate-to-strong confidence. The method was rated 3.9 out of 5 in terms of effectiveness. When asked about applying MCDA in their own contexts, seven participants responded affirmatively, while three indicated they would do so with some caveats.

Despite this overall positive outlook, participants also raised several important concerns regarding its implementation, including:

- The need for fair and transparent weighting processes.
- Risks of subjectivity or bias based on personal or regional perspectives.
- The complexity of handling many indicators.
- The importance of regional adaptation of results.
- A recurring call for sensitivity analysis to improve robustness.

While the use of MCDA to evaluate and prioritise IS solutions presents its limitations, the overall conclusion of the co-creation event was that experts support its use and agree with the weighting factors obtained through the questionnaire.

In terms of future priorities for IS, addressed in Question 5, participants ranked the most relevant focus areas for sustainability as follows:

1. Waste valorisation
2. Regional collaboration
3. Energy recovery
4. Digitalisation

Although digitalisation was ranked lowest, it was described as a cross-cutting enabler of the other three. Beyond identifying future priorities, participants also described a range of ongoing initiatives that reflect their current commitment to IS implementations, translating it into concrete actions:

1. Strengthening networks and partnerships at regional level.
2. Raising awareness and conducting capacity-building activities.
3. Promoting research on waste and by-product valorisation.
4. Using EU project deliverables to identify relevant IS cases.
5. Supporting multi-stakeholder coordination to align territorial strategies.

In summary, the workshop confirmed the relevance of the evaluation model while offering meaningful refinements. The input gathered complemented the questionnaire results with contextual and practical insights, contributing to the development of a more robust and usable IS evaluation framework. These findings directly informed the consolidation of internal and external weightings presented in the following section.

2.2. Final criteria for IS evaluation

To ensure a robust approach for evaluating IS solutions, the results of applying the MCDA methodology in both the internal and external rounds were compared, analysed and subsequently combined. This section explains the steps taken to obtain the final weighting factors for each evaluation criterion of IS solutions.

Table 7 shows the average weightings for the different criteria generated in the two rounds (internal and external) as well as the final weighting. In both cases, the SymRL was ranked first and assigned the highest weighting factor. Similarly, the SRL was ranked last and received the lowest weighting. For these two criteria, the final weighting factor represents a midpoint between the internal and external values: 28% for SymRL and 14% for SRL.

For the ERL, a weighting factor of 25% was assigned during round 1 (internal), ranking it in second place, while in round two (external) it received 18.4%, ranking fourth. However, as highlighted in Section 5.1.2, the experts consulted from industry attributed higher importance to this criterion, ranking it first and assigning it the highest weighting factor of 25.7%. This prioritisation aligns with findings from the literature, where environmental performance is consistently cited as a key driver for organisations and governments to

implement IS solutions. According to Domenech et al. (2019), industrial symbiosis enhances resource efficiency and reduces both waste generation and GHG, contributing to broader circular economy goals. Similarly, Neves et al. (2020) emphasise that environmental benefits —such as reductions in raw material use, emissions, and landfill waste— are significant incentives for government-driven IS initiatives. Likewise, Martin et al. (2014) demonstrate that quantifiable environmental gains play a central role in justifying IS adoption. Based on this evidence, a final weighting factor of 22% was assigned to ERL, ranking as the second most important criterion.

ORL and LRL received equal weighting in both rounds and were placed in the middle of the ranking. Consequently, the final weight for each criterion was calculated as the average of the internal and external rounds values.

Table 7. Average weightings for the criteria generated in the two rounds (internal and external) and final weighting.

Criteria	Internal weighting factor (%)	External weighting factor (%)	Final weighting factor (%)
Symbiosis Readiness Levels (SymRL)	30	26.6	28
Environmental Readiness Levels (ERL)	25	18.4	22
Legal & ethical Readiness Level (LRL)	15	21.1	18
Organisational Readiness Level (ORL)	15	21.4	18
Societal Readiness Level (SRL)	15	11.6	14

3. EVALUATION OF PRIORITISED IS SOLUTIONS

The prioritisation of IS solutions were revisited and evaluated for platforms, methodologies, and approaches using the final weighting factors. Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 show the revisited scoring results obtained for Top IS solutions per category, detailing the new and previous ranking position.

Table 8. Revisited TOP IS Solutions evaluation results for the Platform category. Note: in bold those IS solutions that have changed position in the classification.

IS Solution	Ranking with final weighting factor	New Score	Ranking with previous weighting factor	Previous score
UNIDO: EIP Policy Support Tool	1	3,52	1	3,47
SEEITS	2	3,48	2	3,43
UNIDO: EIP Assessment Tool	3	3,40	3	3,34
Sharebox	4	3,34	4	3,32
Ultimate: Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis	5	3,31	5	3,29
UNIDO: Industrial Symbiosis Identification Tool	6	3,26	7	3,19
UNIDO: EIP Selection Tool	7	3,23	6	3,21
Floow2	8	3,01	8	3,06
Symbiosis Platform / (ICESP) Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	9	2,66	9	2,68
Simbylay	10	2,65	10	2,66

Table 9. Revised TOP IS Solutions evaluation results for Methodologies category. Note: in bold those IS solutions that have changed position in the classification.

IS Solution	Ranking with final weighting factor	New Score	Ranking with previous weighting factor	Previous score
CIRCULAR BIOCARBON: Turning carbon of complex organic urban waste streams into value-added products	1	3,57	1	3,57
Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	2	3,17	2	3,18
FISSAC: Fostering industrial symbiosis for a sustainable resource intensive industry across the extended construction value chain	3	2,95	3	2,99
Uplift: sUustainable PLastics for the Food and drink packaging indusTRy	4	2,81	4	2,78
REDOL: Aragon´s REgional Hub for circularity: Demonstration of Local industrial-urban symbiosis initiatives	5	2,69	5	2,70
SCALER: Scaling European Resources with Industrial Symbiosis	6	2,67	6	2,68

ISIM-TCC Industrial Symbiosis as an Innovative Method in Tackling Climate Change	7	2,65	8	2,66
UBIS - Urban Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	8	2,63	7	2,68
H4C ECoP: Hubs for Circularity European Community of Practice	9	2,48	9	2,47
BeonNAT: Innovative value chains from tree & shrub species grown in marginal lands as a source of biomass for bio-based industries	10	2,33	10	2,36

Table 10. Revised TOP IS Solutions evaluation results for Approaches category. Note: in bold those IS solutions that have changed position in the classification.

IS Solution	Ranking with final weighting factor	New Score	Ranking with previous weighting factor	Previous score
Malmö Cleantech City	1	4,48	1	4,43
Chemical Valley Industrial Area	2	4,42	2	4,42
Ecopark Windhof	3	4,38	4	4,37
EISAP Estonian Industrial Symbiosis Agro-Park	4	4,34	3	4,38
Chemiepark Bitterfeld Wolfen	5	4,30	5	4,28
MABU (Material Business) Project	6	4,19	6	4,22
Händelö Eco Industrial Park	7	4,09	7	4,09
Harjavalta Industrial Eco-Park	8	4,05	8	4,01
Styria Network	9	4,02	10	3,98
Pulawy Production Park	10	3,99	9	4,01

Based on the data presented in the three tables above, it is clear that the application of the final weighting factors led to only minor variations in both the rankings and the scores across the different categories, without altering the top 10 IS solutions in any of them. These findings are consistent with the results previously obtained in D2.3, suggesting that any potential initial bias was not significant, and that the methodology was appropriately designed. Therefore, the current adjustment represents a refinement of the previous weighting factors.

Among the three categories used to classify the IS solutions (approaches, methodologies, and platforms) the approaches category achieved the highest overall scores. Notably, 11 out of the 103 analysed approaches reached a SymRL above 8, a score typically associated with solutions that are nearly market ready. In contrast, none of the IS solutions in the methodologies or platforms categories exceeded a SymRL of 7. This highlights the more advanced stage of development and application observed in the approaches category.

Furthermore, Table 16 in Annex II shows the revisited results obtained for the evaluated IS solutions disregarding category classification. In addition, a dataset containing the full mapping was built and is openly available throughout the Zenodo open repository, available [here](#).

4. GUIDELINES FOR IS IMPLEMENTATION

This section delves into the practical use of the MCDA methodology developed by the SYMBA project, as previously described. The process is divided into five steps as follows (Figure 7):

1. Identification and data collection of the IS solution to evaluate.
2. Application of the evaluation criteria.
3. Application of weighting factors to calculate the single score.
4. Categorisation of the IS solution by maturity level.
5. Analysis to guide strategic action.

These steps are explained in more detail below for the sake of an easy and a straightforward implementation. Finally, a series of recommendations aimed at improving maturity and ensuring a successful implementation of the IS solution are presented.

Figure 7. Steps to apply the MCDA SYMBA methodology.

The aim of the following steps is to provide the user with a robust, data-driven assessment that helps stakeholders understand the maturity and feasibility of IS solutions in a systematic manner.

Step 1: Identification and data collection of the IS solution to evaluate

The first step is to identify the IS solution and collect the necessary data for its evaluation. This foundational step requires a clear definition of the solution's scope and an understanding of its specific application within the industrial ecosystem (waste valorisation, energy recovery, or resource optimisation). Additionally, data must be gathered across all five readiness levels: SymRL, ORL, LRL, SRL, and ERL.

This process may involve reviewing project reports, pilot studies, and case studies, as well as consulting stakeholders with first-hand experience of the solution. It is important to ensure that all data are up-to-date and relevant to the specific context in which the IS solution will be applied.

Step 2: Apply the Evaluation Criteria

Once the IS solution has been defined and the relevant data has been collected, the next step is to apply the evaluation criteria. Each of the five readiness levels shown below is assessed based on predefined scoring definitions, which are detailed in **D3.2 - List and analysis of prioritised industrial symbiosis solutions** and in Annex I of this deliverable.

- **Symbiosis Readiness Level (SymRL)** – Score from 1 to 9, based on maturity in technology, business, ecology, and management dimensions.
- **Organisational Readiness Level (ORL)** – Score from 1 to 5, based on internal capacities and organisational infrastructure.
- **Legal and Ethical Readiness Level (LRL)** – Score from 1 to 5, evaluating legal compliance and ethical alignment.
- **Societal Readiness Level (SRL)** – Score from 1 to 5, assessing stakeholder involvement, social acceptance, and societal impact.
- **Environmental Readiness Level (ERL)** – Score from 1 to 5, assessing sustainability performance and resource efficiency.

Step 3: Apply Weighting Factors

With the evaluation criteria applied, each readiness level is weighted according to its relative importance. These weights, established through stakeholder consultation, are then used to calculate a single score that provides a comprehensive assessment of the solution's overall readiness for implementation. The default SYMBA co-created weights factors are as follows:

- **SymRL:** 28%
- **ERL:** 22%
- **ORL:** 18%
- **LRL:** 18%
- **SRL:** 14%

Step 4: Categorise the IS Solution by Maturity Level

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Based on the final single score, the IS solution is categorised into one of three maturity levels: Beginner, Intermediate, or Advanced. This classification helps to understand the current stage of development and the solution's readiness for market implementation or scale-up.

- **Beginner:** 0.00 to 2.00 – Early-stage, low overall readiness
- **Intermediate:** 2.01 to 4.00 – Moderately developed, some aspects ready
- **Advanced:** Above 4.00 – High readiness and near-market or market-ready solution

Step 5: Analyse Maturity to Guide Strategic Action

The final step involves analysing the assigned maturity category to guide appropriate strategic actions. For Beginner solutions, the focus should be on building foundational capacities and engaging key stakeholders. For Intermediate solutions, actions should target the improvement of specific readiness levels. Advanced solutions should be further assessed for immediate implementation or scale-up.

However, even for solutions categorised as Advanced, it is essential to ensure there are no critical gaps that could hinder implementation. Specifically, if any readiness level scores below 2, this may represent a significant barrier. In such cases, targeted measures should be applied to raise the score of the underperforming readiness level above 2. If these corrective measures fail to produce the expected improvement (i.e., an RL score above 2), the necessary conditions for implementing the IS solution may not yet be in place.

4.1 Tailored recommendations based on maturity

In this subsection, a series of recommendations are provided to help establish next steps and activities based on the maturity level of the IS solution once the MCDA methodology has been applied. The recommendations are broken down according to the three established maturity levels: beginner, intermediate and advanced.

4.1.1 Beginner IS Solutions (0–2)

At this stage, the focus of the activities should be on developing the concept of the IS solution and understanding the feasibility of its validation.

Some recommendations to consider are:

- Invest in pilot testing, stakeholder engagement, and early regulatory mapping.
- Strengthen internal capabilities (ORL) and clarify societal or environmental benefits.
- Seek incubation support or join IS learning networks to accelerate progress.

4.1.2 Intermediate IS Solutions (2–4)

At this stage, the focus of the activities should be demonstrating the applicability of the IS solution and highlighting its benefits. It is also important to refine stakeholder partnerships and collaborative relationships.

Some recommendations to consider are:

- Scale pilot initiatives and develop robust legal and operational models.
- Prioritise stakeholder co-design and environmental performance improvement.
- Apply for funding or partnerships targeting mid-TRL circular economy solutions.

4.1.3 Advanced IS Solutions (>4)

At this stage, the focus should be on market deployment and scaling, as the IS solution is either ready or nearly ready for implementation. Legal (LRL) and societal (SRL) readiness become especially important to ensure all stakeholders understand the benefits, opportunities, and risks associated with full-scale implementation.

Some recommendations to consider are:

- Identify replication opportunities across regions or sectors.
- Formalise partnerships and strengthen data-driven monitoring.
- Showcase the solution in policy dialogues, circular economy hubs, or best-practice platforms.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Within the context of WP3, the SYMBA project successfully applied a MCDA methodology to evaluate and prioritise Industrial Symbiosis (IS) solutions. One of the key findings from this process is that there were no significant differences in the weighting factors between internal and external stakeholders. This consistency indicates that the MCDA approach is both reliable and robust, capturing diverse stakeholder perspectives without introducing bias. The internal co-creation process was effectively complemented by external feedback, ensuring that the methodology is not only inclusive but also scientifically sound and reliable for informed decision-making.

Another critical observation is the consistent ranking of the SymRL as the highest-priority criterion, while the SRL was consistently ranked the lowest. This trend highlights the technical and operational nature of industrial symbiosis evaluations, where immediate feasibility (SymRL) is prioritised over broader societal factors (SRL). This consistent pattern across both internal and external assessments reinforces the reliability of the evaluation process and demonstrates the practicality of focusing on technical readiness when assessing IS solutions.

The findings also affirm that the MCDA methodology is not only robust and unbiased but also replicable. The evaluation process, which produced consistent results across different stakeholder groups, suggests that this methodology can be applied to other IS solutions in different contexts or regions. It provides a scalable framework for prioritising IS solutions based on their readiness for implementation, making it adaptable to various ecosystems across the EU and beyond.

In addition to presenting a comprehensive step-by-step guide on how to apply the MCDA methodology, this deliverable also offers practical recommendations to improve the maturity of IS solutions. These recommendations, particularly for solutions classified as Beginner or Intermediate, focus on actions that support successful implementation of IS solutions. They emphasise the need for enhancing organisational readiness, addressing societal concerns, refining legal frameworks, and improving environmental performance to ensure that IS solutions are not only effective and but also scalable.

In conclusion, the MCDA methodology provides an effective tool for evaluating industrial symbiosis solutions, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions that drive sustainable, resource-efficient, and circular industrial practices.

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7. ANNEXE I: READINESS LEVELS EVALUATION CRITERIA

Table 11. Symbiosis readiness level evaluation criteria.

SYMBIOSIS READINESS LEVEL	TECHNOLOGY	BUSINESS	ECOLOGY	MANAGEMENT
9	Commercialisation	Business case continuously controlled, reported, and shared	Sustainability benefits proven	Resilient partnership
8	Extended operation	Extended operation	Benefits routinely monitored and reported	Practical operation and management start
7	Demonstration	Partners committed	Monitoring and reporting begins	Senior management is involved and supports industrial symbiosis case
6	Prototype demonstration "Looks like"	Business case with all details	Permits applied	Concept for joint management is developed
5	Breadboard demonstration "acts like"	Evaluate competitiveness	Sustainability assessment finalised	Partners start joint evaluation of industrial symbiosis potential
4	Proof of concept validation	Check resources and criteria	Sustainability assessment in progress	Partners indicate interest
3	Proof of concept research (bench scale)	Check fit with strategies of partners	Thorough data collection	First contact with partners
2	Academic research	Develop concept	Rough estimate	Potential partners identified
1	Initial ideas			

Table 12. Organisational readiness level evaluation criteria.

ORL	DESCRIPTION
ORL5	Actual solution proven in relevant organisational environments: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are correctly used for the solution on the market.
ORL4	Actual solution proven in relevant organisational environments: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are correctly used for the solution on the market.
ORL3	Proposed solution validated through pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments. The organisation developing the solution achieves roles, competencies and skills, physical infrastructures required. Solution demonstrated in real-world environments and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback in order to improve roles, processes, functions, and infrastructures required.
ORL2	Comprehensive description of the proposed solution's impacts within the organisation in terms of roles, competencies and skills, physical infrastructures required. Solution validated through simulation of major induced changes to substantiate proposed impacts and organisational readiness. The organisation developing the solution starts to acquire roles, competencies, and skills, physical infrastructures required.
ORL1	Identification of the organisational need (infrastructures, capabilities, skills) and associated organisational readiness aspects. Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; appraisal of organisational readiness issues; identification of relevant roles, processes, functions, and structures for the solution.

Table 13. Legal and ethical readiness level evaluation criteria

SRL	DESCRIPTION
LRL5	Actual solution proven legally and ethically compliant after launch on the market.
LRL4	Refinement of the solution within the existing legal and ethical system and, if needed, proposals for required or recommended changes to some aspects of it. Targeted solution, as well as a legal and ethical compliance audit, complete, qualified, and ready to be launched on the market.
LRL3	Definition of the proposed solution's legal and ethical compliance status after pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments. Detailed description of the required or recommended changes in relevant laws, regulations, or organisational rules to ensure full compliance with the proposed solution.
LRL2	Abstract description of the proposed solution's legal and ethical compliance. Solution's legal and ethical compliance prospects validated against any required or recommended changes in the legal and/or regulatory system.
LRL1	Generic consideration of legal and ethical compliance aspects is observed but nothing has yet been done for the development of the solution. Formulation of the need to enhance the legal normative, laws, rules, and guidelines and solution concept; appraisal of legal and ethical compliance issues.

Table 14. Societal readiness level evaluation criteria.

SRL	DESCRIPTION
SRL5	Actual project solution(s) proven in a relevant environment.
SRL4	Refinement of project and/or solution and, if needed, retesting in relevant environment with relevant stakeholders. Proposed solution(s) as well as a plan for societal adaptation complete and qualified.
SRL3	Proposed solution(s) validated by relevant stakeholders in the area. Solution(s) demonstrated in a relevant environment and in cooperation with relevant stakeholders to gain initial feedback on potential impact.
SRL2	Initial testing of proposed solution(s) together with relevant stakeholders. Problem validated through pilot testing in a relevant environment to substantiate proposed impact and societal readiness.
SRL1	Identifying problems and identifying societal readiness. Formulation of problem, proposed solution(s) and potential impact, expected societal readiness; identifying relevant stakeholders for the project.

Table 15. Environmental readiness level evaluation criteria.

ERL	DESCRIPTION
ERL5	Sustainable feedstock and material supply established.
ERL4	Full-scale producer impact evaluation – Commercialisation.
ERL3	Scale-up validation of initial assessments – Full-scale feedstock impact evaluation.
ERL2	Proof of concept – Preliminary technical evaluation.
ERL1	Basic principles - Concept formulated.

8. ANNEX II: LIST OF EVALUATED AND PRIORITISED IS SOLUTIONS

Table 16. Revisited results obtained for the evaluated IS solutions.

#	Category	IS Solution	ORL	LRL	SRL	ERL	SymRL	Single score
1	Approaches	Malmö Cleantech City	0,9	0,9	0,56	0,88	1,24	4,48
2	Approaches	Chemical Valley Industrial Area	0,9	0,72	0,42	1,1	1,28	4,42
3	Approaches	Ecopark Windhof	0,72	0,9	0,56	0,88	1,32	4,38
4	Approaches	EISAP Estonian Industrial Symbiosis Agro-Park	0,72	0,72	0,56	1,1	1,24	4,34
5	Approaches	Chemiepark Bitterfeld Wolfen	0,9	0,72	0,56	0,88	1,24	4,3
6	Approaches	MABU (Material Business) Project	0,72	0,72	0,56	1,1	1,09	4,19
7	Approaches	Händelö Eco Industrial Park	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,88	1,21	4,09
8	Approaches	Harjavalta Industrial Eco-Park	0,72	0,9	0,42	0,88	1,13	4,05
9	Approaches	Styria Network	0,72	0,9	0,28	0,88	1,24	4,02
10	Approaches	Pulawy Production Park	0,72	0,72	0,56	1,1	0,89	3,99
11	Approaches	Basf Verbund site Ludwigshafen	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,88	1,24	3,98
12	Approaches	Industriepark Kalle Albert	0,9	0,72	0,42	0,88	1,05	3,97
13	Approaches	PLENITUDE Flahsip	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,88	1,09	3,97
14	Approaches	Chemiepark Delfzijl	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,88	1,21	3,95
15	Approaches	Chempark Dormagen	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,88	1,21	3,95
16	Approaches	Production synergies in the current biofuel industry: opportunities for development; Michael Martin	0,9	0,9	0,56	0,66	0,93	3,95
17	Approaches	Rietvelden - De Vutter	0,54	0,72	0,56	0,88	1,21	3,91
18	Approaches	Ecopark Hartberg	0,54	0,54	0,7	0,88	1,24	3,9
19	Approaches	Landskrona Industrial Symbiosis	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,17	3,87
20	Approaches	Rantasalmi	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,88	0,97	3,85
21	Approaches	Galaxia Industrial Park	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,13	3,83
22	Approaches	Marl Chemical Park	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,13	3,83
23	Approaches	Pharma und Chemiepark Wuppertal	0,72	0,72	0,28	0,88	1,21	3,81
24	Approaches	Polígono O Ceao	0,72	0,72	0,28	0,88	1,21	3,81
25	Approaches	Circular economy in Romania; An industrial synergy in the agri-food sector	0,72	0,54	0,28	1,1	1,13	3,77
26	Approaches	Norrköping and Linköping	0,36	0,72	0,56	0,88	1,24	3,76
27	Approaches	Polígono Industrial El Congost	0,54	0,9	0,56	0,66	1,09	3,75
28	Approaches	Chemical Industrial Park Knapsack	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,66	1,21	3,73
29	Approaches	Parc de l'Alba	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,66	1,05	3,71

30	Approaches	Santa Perpètua de Mogoda industrial area	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,01	3,71
31	Approaches	Biopark Terneuzen	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,88	1,13	3,69
32	Approaches	Gewerbenetzwerk Pfaffengrund	0,54	0,72	0,56	0,66	1,21	3,69
33	Approaches	Créalys® Scientific Park	0,54	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,13	3,65
34	Approaches	KALUNDBORG, Industrial symbiosis	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,66	1,17	3,65
35	Approaches	Zero Emission Park Kaiserslautern	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,66	1,09	3,61
36	Approaches	Monstera	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,93	3,59
37	Approaches	South Groningen Business Park	0,72	0,54	0,7	0,88	0,74	3,58
38	Approaches	Zero Emission Park Bremen	0,36	0,36	0,7	0,88	1,28	3,58
39	Approaches	Lucento Industrial Area	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,88	1,01	3,57
40	Methodologies	CIRCULAR BIOCARBON: Turning carbon of complex organic urban waste streams into value-added products	0,72	0,54	0,56	0,66	1,09	3,57
41	Approaches	Bayer Industrial Park Brunsbüttel	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,21	3,55
42	Approaches	Chempark Leverkusen	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,88	1,17	3,55
43	Approaches	Dow Valuepark	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,88	1,17	3,55
44	Approaches	Oberbruch Industry Park	0,72	0,36	0,56	0,88	1,01	3,53
45	Approaches	San Daniele s.c.a.r.l Agrifood Park	0,54	0,72	0,56	0,66	1,05	3,53
46	Platforms	UNIDO: EIP Policy Support Tool	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,86	3,52
47	Approaches	Zero Emission Park Bottrop	0,72	0,72	0,7	0,44	0,93	3,51
48	Approaches	Systemic Analysis of the Contributions of Co-Located Industrial Symbiosis to Achieve Sustainable Development in an Industrial Park in Northern Spain	0,72	0,54	0,28	0,88	1,09	3,51
49	Platforms	SEEITS	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,82	3,48
50	Approaches	Industriepark Höchst	0,54	0,54	0,56	0,66	1,17	3,47
51	Approaches	Parque Tecnológico Galicia Tecnópolis	0,72	0,54	0,28	0,88	1,05	3,47
52	Approaches	Navicelli di Pisa Park	0,54	0,54	0,7	0,66	1,01	3,45
53	Approaches	Gertshofen Industriepark	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,09	3,43
54	Approaches	Havre Industrial-Harbour Park	0,54	0,36	0,56	0,88	1,09	3,43
55	Approaches	Honeywell Seelze	0,72	0,36	0,42	0,88	1,05	3,43
56	Approaches	Plaine de l'Ain Industrial Park	0,54	0,54	0,56	0,66	1,13	3,43
57	Approaches	Polígono industrial de Alfacar	0,72	0,54	0,7	0,66	0,78	3,4
58	Platforms	UNIDO: EIP Assessment Tool	0,72	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,74	3,4
59	Approaches	Emmtec Industry & Business Park	0,72	0,54	0,28	0,88	0,97	3,39
60	Approaches	Tenneville Industrial Park	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,66	1,05	3,39
61	Approaches	Schwedt Industrial Park	0,36	0,72	0,42	0,66	1,21	3,37
62	Approaches	InfraLeuna	0,54	0,36	0,56	0,66	1,24	3,36

63	Approaches	Landskrona: Industrial symbiosis networks and the contribution to environmental innovation: The case of the Landskrona industrial symbiosis programme	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,66	1,01	3,35
64	Platforms	Sharebox	0,54	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,86	3,34
65	Approaches	Torvilliers Industrial Park	0,18	0,54	0,56	0,88	1,17	3,33
66	Approaches	Roche en Brènil Wood Ecopole	0,36	0,72	0,42	0,88	0,93	3,31
67	Platforms	Ultimate: Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,66	0,97	3,31
68	Approaches	Lagny-sur-Marne and La Courtilière Industrial Parks	0,36	0,72	0,56	0,88	0,74	3,26
69	Platforms	UNIDO: Industrial Symbiosis Identification Tool	0,72	0,72	0,42	0,66	0,74	3,26
70	Approaches	Port of Rotterdam	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,09	3,25
71	Approaches	Moerdijk	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,66	0,89	3,23
72	Platforms	UNIDO: EIP Selection Tool	0,54	0,72	0,42	0,66	0,89	3,23
73	Approaches	Les Sohettes Bio-refinery	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,05	3,21
74	Approaches	Prato 1st Industrial Macrolotto	0,72	0,9	0,28	0,22	1,09	3,21
75	Approaches	Relvão Eco-Industrial Park	0,72	0,36	0,56	0,66	0,89	3,19
76	Approaches	BASAJAUN: Building A SustainAble Joint between rural and Urban Areas Through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains	0,54	0,54	0,56	0,44	1,09	3,17
77	Approaches	Ecolys® Park	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,44	1,05	3,17
78	Approaches	Police Industrial Park	0,72	0,36	0,28	0,88	0,93	3,17
79	Approaches	Park no. 56: Zero Emission Park Bottrop	0,36	0,54	0,56	0,66	1,05	3,17
80	Methodologies	Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,01	3,17
81	Approaches	Polígono As Gándaras	0,36	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,86	3,16
82	Approaches	Jämtland County	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,44	1,21	3,15
83	Approaches	Chemie-und Industriepark Zeitz	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,66	0,97	3,13
84	Approaches	Grand Troyes Park	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,44	1,01	3,13
85	Approaches	Technopôle Savoie Technolac	0,54	0,36	0,56	0,66	0,97	3,09
86	Approaches	Nogent Industrial Basin	0,18	0,72	0,56	0,66	0,93	3,05
87	Approaches	ResiSt Project. Is part of the UNEP Urban Resilience program	0,72	0,54	0,42	0,44	0,93	3,05
88	Approaches	Envipark (Parco Scientifico Tecnologico per l'Ambiente)	0,72	0,36	0,42	0,44	1,09	3,03
89	Approaches	Kaiserbaracke Industrial Park	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,88	1,01	3,03
90	Approaches	Padova Industrial Park	0,54	0,54	0,42	0,44	1,09	3,03
91	Approaches	Deux Synthe Industrial Park	0,36	0,72	0,14	0,66	1,13	3,01
92	Platforms	Floow2	0,54	0,36	0,56	0,66	0,89	3,01
93	Approaches	Cairo Montenotte Industrial Park	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,66	1,01	2,99

94	Approaches	Kymi Eco-industrial Park	0,72	0,18	0,42	0,66	1,01	2,99
95	Approaches	Uimaharju Industrial Area	0,72	0,18	0,42	0,88	0,78	2,98
96	Approaches	Ponte Rizzoli Industrial Park	0,54	0,54	0,7	0,44	0,74	2,96
97	Approaches	Parque tecnológico y logístico de Vigo	0,36	0,54	0,56	0,44	1,05	2,95
98	Methodologies	FISSAC: Fostering industrial symbiosis for a sustainable resource intensive industry across the extended construction value chain	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,66	0,97	2,95
99	Approaches	Amaro Industrial Park	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,66	1,01	2,81
100	Methodologies	Uplift: sUustainable PLastics for the Food and drink packaging indusTRY	0,54	0,54	0,28	0,44	1,01	2,81
101	Approaches	SYMBI: Industrial symbiosis for Regional Sustainable Growth and a Resource Efficient Circular Economy	0,54	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,97	2,77
102	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 1. Tarragona. Increasing the capacity to recover water at an industrial complex	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,44	1,01	2,77
103	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 5: Lleida, Ostrava. Water recycling in the beverage industry	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	1,09	2,71
104	Methodologies	REDOL: Aragón's REgional Hub for circularity: Demonstration of Local industrial-urban symbiosis initiatives	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,44	0,93	2,69
105	Methodologies	SCALER: Scaling European Resources with Industrial Symbiosis	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	1,05	2,67
106	Approaches	Camp CO2-Zero	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,66	0,82	2,66
107	Platforms	Symbiosis Platform / (ICESP) Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,66	0,82	2,66
108	Methodologies	ISIM-TCC Industrial Symbiosis as an Innovative Method in Tackling Climate Change	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,44	0,89	2,65
109	Platforms	Simbylay	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,44	0,89	2,65
110	Platforms	Watersmart	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,66	0,66	2,64
111	Methodologies	UBIS - Urban Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,44	1,05	2,63
112	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 4: Nafplio. Mobile wastewater treatment unit	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	1,01	2,63
113	Platforms	Maestri	0,54	0,36	0,42	0,44	0,86	2,62
114	Platforms	EPOS	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,44	1,01	2,59
115	Approaches	Boruta Zgierz Industrial Park	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,44	0,97	2,55
116	Approaches	Sustainable Knowledge-Portal on Water-Smartness and Circular Economy (CE) solutions	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,89	2,51
117	Methodologies	H4C ECoP: Hubs for Circularity European Community of Practice	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,86	2,48

118	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 2. Water reuse and heat recovery for horticulture	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,86	2,48
119	Approaches	PlastiCircle: Improvement of the plastic packaging waste chain from a circular economy approach	0,36	0,36	0,42	0,44	0,89	2,47
120	Platforms	Unido: EIP Opportunities Monitoring Tool	0,54	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,66	2,46
121	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 3. Rosignano. Water reuse and material recovery in the chemical industry	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,97	2,41
122	Platforms	Simval	0,36	0,54	0,42	0,44	0,62	2,38
123	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 6: Karmiel and Shafdan	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,93	2,37
124	Approaches	Felsenpark	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,44	0,74	2,36
125	Methodologies	BeonNAT: Innovative value chains from tree & shrub species grown in marginal lands as a source of biomass for bio-based industries	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,89	2,33
126	Approaches	AgriMAX: Agri and food waste valorisation co-ops based on flexible multi-feedstocks biorefinery processing technologies for new high added value applications	0,18	0,36	0,42	0,44	0,86	2,26
127	Methodologies	SPIRE-SAIS: Skills Alliance for Industrial Symbiosis- a Cross-sectoral Blueprint for a Sustainable Process Industry	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,97	2,19
128	Methodologies	ELLIPSE: Efficient and Novel Waste Streams Co-processing to Obtain Bio-based Solutions for Packaging and Agricultural Sector	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,74	2,18
129	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 9: Kalondborg. Strengthening water, energy and amterial reuse at the Kalundborg Industrial Symbiosis	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,93	2,15
130	Approaches	Thams Klyngen and Naeringsagen i Orkdalsregionen	0,18	0,36	0,28	0,22	1,09	2,13
131	Approaches	Eko-park d.o.o Lendava	0,36	0,18	0,28	0,44	0,86	2,12
132	Approaches	Ultimate: case study 7: Tain, United Kingdem Water recycling, energy recovery and material recovery in distilleries	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,89	2,11
133	Methodologies	KARMA2020: Industrial Feather Waste Valorisation for Sustainable KeRatin based MAterials	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,66	2,1
134	Methodologies	CISUTAC: Circular & Sustainable Textiles & Clothing	0,36	0,54	0,28	0,22	0,66	2,06
135	Platforms	eSymbiosis	0,36	0,36	0,14	0,44	0,74	2,04
136	Methodologies	TRIS: Transition Regions towards Industrial Symbiosis	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,78	2

137	Methodologies	SYMSITES: Industrial Urban Symbiosis and its social, economic and environmental impact on different European regions	0,36	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,74	1,96
138	Methodologies	CORALIS: Creation of new value chain Relations through novel Approaches facilitating Long-term Industrial Symbiosis	0,36	0,54	0,14	0,22	0,66	1,92
139	Platforms	Indusym	0,18	0,36	0,28	0,44	0,62	1,88
140	Approaches	Croix-Fort Artisanal Park	0,36	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,78	1,86
141	Approaches	ECOMARK - turning environmental challenges into opportunities	0,18	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,66	1,7
142	Approaches	Ultimate: Case Study 8: Saint-Maurice l'Exil. Heat and Resource recovery in chemical incineration plant	0,18	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,78	1,68
143	Approaches	Cicle	0,18	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,7	1,6
144	Approaches	CO2 utilization in the perspective of industrial ecology, an overview; F.D. Meylan	0,36	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,51	1,59
145	Methodologies	SYM-CRAFT	0,18	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,66	1,56
146	Approaches	Industrial symbiosis networks and the contribution to environmental innovation: The case of the Landskrona industrial symbiosis programme	0,18	0,36	0,28	0,22	0,51	1,55
147	Approaches	ACCSION	0,18	0,18	0,28	0,22	0,66	1,52
148	Methodologies	SymNet Industrial Symbiosis Network for Environment Protection and Sustainable Development in Black Sea Basin	0,18	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,62	1,52
149	Platforms	The Cambridge Value Mapping Tool	0,18	0,18	0,28	0,44	0,43	1,51
150	Platforms	Siner	0,18	0,36	0,14	0,22	0,43	1,33
151	Methodologies	ECOREG	0,18	0,18	0,28	0,22	0,43	1,29
152	Methodologies	CIRC-PACK: Towards Circular Economy in the Plastic Packaging Value Chain	0,18	0,18	0,14	0,22	0,51	1,23
153	Methodologies	CircClean	0,18	0,18	0,14	0,22	0,43	1,15
154	Platforms	Metropolitan area industrial symbiosis programme providing tools for municipalities and businesses	0,18	0,18	0,14	0,22	0,39	1,11
155	Methodologies	NISP: National Industrial Symbiosis Programme UK	0,18	0,18	0,14	0,22	0,35	1,07

